

Multi-component reactions of formyl-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins under microwave irradiation

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Abstract : Ethylacetoacetate and ammonia/urea were reacted with formyl-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins 2a-e by microwave irradiation to give 1,4-dihydropyridyl-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins 3a-e/3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-one-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins (Biginelli compounds) 4a-e respectively. These compounds have been screened for their potential as microbial growth inhibitors against six bacterial and six fungal strains. The growth inhibition was observed against the Gram positive species and all the fungal strains even at a concentration of 6.25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in some cases.

Keywords : Coumarin, 1,4-dihydropyridine, 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-one, Biginelli reaction, Hantzsch condensation, 4-bromomethylcoumarin.

Introduction

Multi-component chemical reactions (MCR) have attracted the attention of chemists since this strategy enables the creation of structural diversity on any molecular skeleton merging two or more steps in a synthetic sequence¹⁻³. Application of microwave irradiation (MWI) has added a new dimension to organic synthesis and drug discovery process in an environmental friendly manner⁴⁻⁶. Microwave assisted multi-component reactions have been reported for the synthesis of pyrroles⁷ and 1,2-*a* fused imidazoles⁸. Solution phase microwave irradiation technique has been applied for the three component Hantzsch synthesis of 1,4-dihydropyridines^{9,10} acting as anti-tubercular¹¹, calcium channel antagonistic¹², cytotoxic¹³ and multiple drug resistance agents¹⁴. The Biginelli reaction leading to 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-ones has been reported under the influence of metal catalysts¹⁵, ionic liquids¹⁶, boric acid¹⁷, polymer supports¹⁸ and microwave irradiation¹⁹ using polyphosphate esters as the reaction mediators. Introduction of a flavone moiety at the C-4 position of the 1,4-dihydropyridine nucleus has resulted in compounds selective for the cardiac tissues acting as calcium channel modulators²⁰. The interesting photophysical and biological properties associated with the paracetamol²¹

and vanillin ethers²² from 4-bromomethylcoumarins is the basis for the present investigation. The present paper, thus, reports the microwave assisted three component-coupling reactions of formyl-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins to obtain 1,4-dihydropyridine-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins and 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-one-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins, in the absence of any metal catalysts.

Results and discussion

The required 4-bromomethylcoumarins²³ 1a-e were prepared by Pechmann cyclisation of phenols with 4-bromoethylacetoacetate. This was followed by room temperature allylic nucleophilic substitution with *m*-formylphenol leading to the formation of formyl-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins²⁴ 2a-e. The reactivity of the formyl group in these compounds has been exploited to construct 1,4-dihydropyridine and 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-one moieties.

The first scheme describes our efforts to apply Hantzsch condensation reaction on the formyl-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins 2a-e. The other two components used for this purpose were ethylacetoacetate and liquor ammonia. The reactants were taken in 1 : 2 : 10 ratio and subjected to thermal refluxing in DMF over a period of 8-12 h which

did not result in any reaction. Compounds **2a-e** were re-covered unchanged. This three components reaction mixture was then subjected to microwave irradiation using a domestic microwave oven employing an open vessel system. The time and yield optimization experiments were performed to standardize the reaction conditions. The present investigation has shown that the time required was 4 min, to obtain maximum yields in the range of 85–92%. The work up procedure for the reaction mixture was to dilute with a ten-fold excess of ice water, which resulted in the separation of colourless solid. These compounds were purified by crystallization. The products obtained **3a-e** can be systematically named as 2,6-dimethyl-4-[3-(2-oxo-2*H*-chromen-4-yl-methoxy)-phenyl]-1,4-dihydro-pyridine-3,5-dicarboxylic acid diethyl ester (Scheme 1).

The second scheme describes our efforts to apply Biginelli reaction on the formyl-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins **2a-e**. The other two components were ethylacetoacetate and urea. The reactants were mixed in the ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 in DMF and subjected to microwave irradiation using a domestic microwave oven in an open vessel system. The required reaction time to obtain maximum yield was four minutes. The work up and purification methods were similar to as described under first scheme. The products obtained **4a-e** can be systematically named as 6-methyl-2-oxo-4-[3-(2-oxo-2*H*-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-pyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (Scheme 1).

In the IR spectrum of 2,6-dimethyl-4-[3-(2-oxo-2*H*-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-1,4-dihydro-pyridine-3,5-dicarboxylic acid diethyl ester **3a**, the lactone carbonyl

a, R = 6-CH₃; b, R = 7-CH₃; c, R = 5,6-benzo; d, R = 6-OCH₃; e, R = Cl

Scheme 1

stretching frequency was observed at 1720 cm^{-1} . The two ester carbonyl stretching frequencies in 1,4-dihydropyridine moiety were observed at 1686 cm^{-1} and 1671 cm^{-1} . The NH stretching frequency was observed at 3338 cm^{-1} . In the PMR spectrum of compound **3a**, a singlet at δ 2.32 (3H) was observed due to $\text{C}_6\text{-CH}_3$ protons. The $\text{C}_4\text{-CH}_2$ protons were observed down field as singlet at δ 5.1 (2H). The $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$ of coumarin appeared as a singlet at δ 6.67 (1H). The aromatic protons of coumarin and phenyl ring resonated as a multiplet in the region of δ 6.75–8.01 (7H). The two CH_3 group protons of 1,4-dihydropyridine ring appeared as a singlet at δ 2.1 (6H). The two carbethoxymethylene protons appeared at δ 4.1 (4H, J 6.9 Hz) as a quartet and the two CH_3 group protons at δ 1.2 (6H, J 6.9 Hz) as a triplet. The methine proton of 1,4-dihydropyridine ring appeared as a singlet at δ 6.09 (1H). The NH proton appeared as a singlet at δ 10.01 (1H), which was confirmed by D_2O exchange. The mass spectra (FAB) of compound **3a** showed (M+H) peak at 518 (15%), where as the base peak appeared at m/z 252 (100%) which corresponds to the 1,4-dihydropyridine moiety resulting after the loss of the 4-aryloxymethylcoumarin fragment by the homolytic cleavage of Ar-C bond.

In the IR spectrum of 6-methyl-2-oxo-4-[3-(2-oxo-2H-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-pyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (Biginelli compound) **4a**, the lactone carbonyl stretching frequency was observed at 1720 cm^{-1} . The ester carbonyl and amide carbonyl stretching frequencies in 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-one moiety were observed at 1690 cm^{-1} and 1640 cm^{-1} respectively. The two NH stretching frequencies were observed at 3345 cm^{-1} and 3233 cm^{-1} . In the PMR spectrum of compound **4a**, a singlet at δ 2.4 (3H) was observed due to $\text{C}_6\text{-CH}_3$ protons. The $\text{C}_4\text{-CH}_2$ protons were observed down field as singlet at δ 5.4 (2H). The $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$ of coumarin proton appeared as a singlet at δ 6.49 (1H). The aromatic protons of coumarin and phenyl group were resonated as a multiplet in the region of δ 6.88–7.74 (7H). The CH_3 protons of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-one ring appeared as a singlet at δ 2.32 (3H). The carbethoxymethylene protons appeared at δ 3.96 (2H, J 6.9 Hz) as a quartet and the methyl protons at δ 1.08 (3H, J 6.9 Hz) as a triplet. The methine proton of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-one ring appeared as a singlet at δ 5.13 (1H). The NH proton appeared as a singlet at δ 9.19 (1H), which was confirmed by D_2O exchange. The mass spectra (EI) of compound **4a** ($\text{R} = 6\text{-CH}_3$) showed

molecular ion peak at m/z 448 (10%) where as the base peak appeared at m/z 183 (100%) due to 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-one moiety, resulting after the loss of the 4-aryloxymethylcoumarin fragment as observed in the case of **3a**.

In vitro antimicrobial activity :

The standard strains were procured from the microbial type culture collection and Gene Bank (MTCC), Institute of Microbial Technology, Chandigarh, India. The anti-bacterial activities of the synthesized compounds were performed by broth micro dilution method^{25,26} against the following standard bacterial strains : *S. aureus* (MTCC 3160), *S. epidermidis* (MTCC 3382), *Bacillus Sp.* (MTCC 297), *P. aeruginosa* (MTCC 1034), *E. coli* (MTCC 1089) and *Klebsiella Sp.* (MTCC 3384). The antifungal activity was performed against the following standard fungal strains : *Penicillium chrysogenum*, *Rhizopus oryzae*, *Mucor fuscus*, *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Aspergillus niger*.

In vitro antibacterial assay :

The MICs of the synthesized compounds determined against Gram positive (*S. aureus*, *S. epidermidis* and *Bacillus Sp.*) and Gram negative bacteria (*P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli* and *Klebsiella Sp.*) were determined by broth microdilution method^{25,26} using Ciprofloxacin as the standard. A control was performed with the test medium supplemented with DMSO at the same dilutions as used in the experiments.

In vitro antifungal assay :

The MICs of the synthesized compounds determined against *Penicillium chrysogenum*, *Rhizopus oryzae*, *Mucor fuscus*, *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Aspergillus niger* were determined by broth microdilution method^{25,26} using Gresiofulvin as the standard. A control was performed with the test medium supplemented with DMSO at the same dilutions as used in the experiments.

Newly synthesized compounds **3a-e** and **4a-e** were evaluated for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against three Gram positive bacteria and three Gram negative bacteria by convention agar dilution procedures and the results of these assays are summarized in Table 1. The observation from the antibacterial activity of 1,4-pyridyl-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins **3a-e** does not show any activity (MIC : 50–100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) to Ciprofloxacin against tested bacteria. They are weakly active compounds. In the case of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-one-4-aryloxymethyl-

Table 1. *In vitro* antibacterial activity of the compounds 3a-e and 4a-e : MIC in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$

Compd.	R	Gram-positive			Gram-negative		
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Bacillus Sp.</i>	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Klebsiella</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
3a	6-CH ₃	> 100	> 100	50	> 100	> 100	> 100
3b	7-CH ₃	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
3c	5,6-benzo	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
3d	6-OCH ₃	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
3e	6-Cl	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
4a	6-CH ₃	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
4b	7-CH ₃	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
4c	5,6-benzo	12.5	12.5	12.5	> 100	> 100	> 100
4d	6-OCH ₃	> 100	50	50	> 100	> 100	> 100
4e	6-Cl	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
Ciprofloxacin		8	8	4	4	4	8

MIC-Minimum Inhibitory Concentration.

coumarins, compound 4c (R = 5,6-benzo) showed considerable activity (MIC : 12.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) against Gram positive bacteria *S. aureus*, *Bacillus Sp.* and *S. epidermidis*. The remaining compounds are weakly active (MIC : 50–100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) compounds.

The results of antifungal study (Table 2) showed that the 1,4-dihydropyridyl-4-aryloxymethylcoumarin 3a (R = 6-CH₃) is equipotent (MIC : 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) to Gresiofulvin against *A. fumigatus* and *A. niger*. The remaining com-

6.25–25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) against *R. oryzae*, *M. fuscus* and *C. albicans*. Compounds 4a, 4c and 4d showed more activity (MIC : 12.5–25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) against *A. fumigatus* and *A. niger*.

In general, 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-one-4-aryloxy-methylcoumarins are more active compounds than 1,4-dihydropyridyl-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins. 3,4-Dihydropyrimidin-2-one-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins are better antifungals than antibacterials.

Table 2. *In vitro* antifungal activity of compounds 3a-e and 4a-e : MIC in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$

Compd.	R	<i>P. chrysogenum</i>	<i>R. oryzae</i>	<i>M. fuscus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
3a	6-CH ₃	100	100	50	> 100	50	50
3b	7-CH ₃	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
3c	5,6-benzo	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
3d	6-OCH ₃	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
3e	6-Cl	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100	> 100
4a	6-CH ₃	12.5	50	50	> 100	25	25
4b	7-CH ₃	50	50	50	> 100	> 100	> 100
4c	5,6-benzo	≤ 6.25	≤ 6.25	≤ 6.25	25	25	25
4d	6-OCH ₃	12.5	12.5	25	12.5	12.5	12.5
4e	6-Cl	100	100	50	> 100	100	100
Gresiofulvin		25	25	25	100	50	50

MIC-Minimum Inhibitory Concentration.

pounds are weakly active compounds (MIC : 50–100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). But 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-one-4-aryloxymethylcoumarins 4a, 4c, 4d showed more activity (MIC : 6.25–12.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) to Gresiofulvin against *P. chrysogenum*. Compounds 4c and 4d showed more activity (MIC :

Experimental

Melting points were determined using an electric melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Kenstar BPL domestic microwave oven was used. IR spectra were run in KBr pellets on a Nicolet Impact-410 FT-IR spectro-

meter (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}). ^1H NMR and D_2O -exchange spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 and $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ with TMS as an internal standard (chemical shift in δ ppm, J values in Hz) on a Bruker 300 MHz FTNMR spectrometer. EI and FAB Mass spectra were recorded from Indian Institute of Chemical Technology, Hyderabad. Elemental analyses were carried out on a Heraeus CHN Rapid analyser. Purity of the compound was checked by TLC structures were drawn using Chem. Draw Ultra version 6.0. All the reagents were of laboratory reagent quality and were purchased from Sd.fine-chemicals Limited and used after purification.

General procedure for synthesis of 4-bromomethylcoumarins (1a-e) and 3-(2-oxo-2H-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)benzaldehydes (2a-e) :

These were prepared according to the earlier literature methods^{23,24}.

General procedure for synthesis of 2,6-dimethyl-4-[3-(2-oxo-2H-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-1,4-dihydro-pyridine-3,5-dicarboxylic acid diethyl esters (3a-e) :

A mixture of compounds 2a-e (0.1 mol), ethylacetoacetate (6.4 ml, 0.5 mol) and excess of ammonia (10 ml) and conc. HCl (1 ml) in DMF (50 ml) was taken in a 250 ml Borosil beaker and zapped inside a microwave oven for 4 min (60% M.W. Power). The reaction mixture was cooled and poured onto crushed ice, neutralized with 20 ml of 10% HCl. The separated solid was filtered, washed with cold ethanol, dried and recrystallised from DMF.

2,6-Dimethyl-4-[3-(6-methyl-2-oxo-2H-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-1,4-dihydro-pyridine-3,5-dicarboxylic acid diethyl ester (3a) :

Colourless crystals, yield 92%, m.p. 176–178 °C; ν_{\max} (KBr) : 1720 (lactone C=O), 1686 (ester C=O), 1671 (ester C=O), 1576 (C=C), 3338 (NH) cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 1.20 (6H, t, J 6.9 Hz, CH_3 of COOC_2H_5), 2.1 (6H, s, CH_3 of Py), 2.32 (3H, s, $\text{C}_6\text{-CH}_3$), 4.1 (4H, q, J 6.9 Hz, CH_2 of COOC_2H_5), 5.1 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 6.09 (1H, s, CH of Py), 6.67 (1H, s, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$), 6.75–8.01 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.01 (1H, s, NH, D_2O -exchangeable) ppm; m/z (%) 518 (M+H, 15), 472 (40), 252 (100) (Found : C, 69.31; H, 5.67; N, 2.38. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{31}\text{O}_7\text{N}$ Calcd. : C, 69.63; H, 5.99; N, 2.70%).

2,6-Dimethyl-4-[3-(7-methyl-2-oxo-2H-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-1,4-dihydro-pyridine-3,5-dicarboxylic acid diethyl ester (3b) :

Colourless crystals, yield 92%, m.p. 144–146 °C;

ν_{\max} (KBr) : 1715 (lactone C=O), 1696 (ester C=O), 1653 (ester C=O), 1505 (C=C), 3357 (NH) cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 1.28 (6H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH_3 of COOC_2H_5), 2.32 (6H, s, CH_3 of Py), 2.46 (3H, s, $\text{C}_6\text{-CH}_3$), 4.18 (4H, q, J 7.2 Hz, CH_2 of COOC_2H_5), 5.16 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 5.68 (1H, s, CH of Py), 6.60 (1H, s, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$), 6.73–8.69 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.0 (1H, s, NH, D_2O -exchangeable) ppm (Found : C, 69.36; H, 5.69; N, 2.37. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{31}\text{O}_7\text{N}$ Calcd. : C, 69.63; H, 5.99; N, 2.70%).

*2,6-Dimethyl-4-[3-(3-oxo-3H-benzo[*ff*]chromen-1-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-1,4-dihydro-pyridine-3,5-dicarboxylic acid diethyl ester (3c) :*

Colourless crystals, yield 94%, m.p. 166–168 °C; ν_{\max} (KBr) : 1733 (lactone C=O), 1690 (ester C=O), 1647 (ester C=O), 1551 (C=C), 3333 (NH) cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : 1.20 (6H, t, J 6.9 Hz, CH_3 of COOC_2H_5), 2.29 (6H, s, CH_3 of Py), 4.07 (4H, q, J 6.9 Hz, CH_2 of COOC_2H_5), 4.99 (1H, s, NH, D_2O -exchangeable), 5.56 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 5.59 (1H, s, CH of Py), 6.78 (1H, s, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$), 6.94–8.18 (10H, m, Ar-H) ppm (Found : C, 71.29; H, 5.30; N, 2.21. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{31}\text{O}_7\text{N}$ Calcd. : C, 71.58; H, 5.60; N, 2.53%).

4-[3-(6-Methoxy-2-oxo-2H-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-pyridine-3,5-dicarboxylic acid diethyl ester (3d) :

Colourless crystals, yield 98%, m.p. 148–150 °C; ν_{\max} (KBr) : 1727 (lactone C=O), 1713 (ester C=O), 1698 (ester C=O), 1525 (C=C), 3341 (NH) cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (300 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : 1.26 (6H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH_3 of COOC_2H_5), 2.42 (6H, s, CH_3 of Py), 3.87 (3H, s, $\text{C}_6\text{-OCH}_3$), 4.28 (4H, q, J 7.2 Hz, CH_2 of COOC_2H_5), 5.21 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 5.27 (1H, s, CH of Py), 6.65 (1H, s, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$), 6.83–7.54 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.0 (1H, s, NH, D_2O -exchangeable) ppm (Found : C, 67.21; H, 5.50; N, 2.31. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{31}\text{O}_8\text{N}$ Calcd. : C, 67.54; H, 5.81; N, 2.62%).

4-[3-(6-Chloro-2-oxo-2H-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-2,6-dimethyl-1,4-dihydro-pyridine-3,5-dicarboxylic acid diethyl ester (3e) :

Colourless crystals, yield 86%, m.p. 188–190 °C; ν_{\max} (KBr) : 1726 (lactone C=O), 1705 (ester C=O), 1692 (ester C=O), 1509 (C=C), 3346 (NH) cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (300 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : 1.26 (6H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH_3 of COOC_2H_5), 2.43 (6H, s, CH_3 of Py), 4.26 (4H, q, J 7.2 Hz, CH_2 of COOC_2H_5), 5.35 (2H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{-O}$), 5.44 (1H, s, CH of Py), 6.70 (1H, s, $\text{C}_3\text{-H}$), 7.27–7.97 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.01 (1H, s, NH, D_2O -exchangeable) ppm

(Found : C, 67.21; H, 5.50; N, 2.31. $C_{29}H_{28}O_7NCl$
Calcd. : C, 67.54; H, 5.81; N, 2.62%).

General procedure for synthesis of 6-methyl-2-oxo-4-[3-(2-oxo-2H-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-pyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid ethyl esters (Biginelli compounds) (4a-e) :

A mixture of compounds **2a-e** (0.1 mol), ethylacetate (1.3 ml, 0.1 mol), urea (0.6 g, 0.1 mol) and conc. HCl (1 ml) in DMF (50 ml) was taken in a 250 ml Borosil beaker and zapped inside a microwave oven for 4 min (60% M.W. Power). The reaction mixture was cooled and poured onto crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered, washed with cold ethanol, dried and recrystallised from DMF.

6-Methyl-4-[3-(6-methyl-2-oxo-2H-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-pyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (4a) :

Colourless crystals, yield 91%, m.p. 290–292 °C; ν_{max} (KBr) : 1720 (lactone C=O), 1690 (ester C=O), 1640 (amide C=O), 1572 (C=C), 3345 (NH), 3233 (NH) cm^{-1} ; δ_H (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : 1.08 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz, CH_3 of $COOC_2H_5$), 2.22 (3H, s, CH_3 of Py-2-one), 2.40 (3H, s, C_6-CH_3), 3.96 (2H, q, *J* 6.9 Hz, CH_2 of $COOC_2H_5$), 5.13 (1H, s, CH of Py-2-one), 5.40 (2H, s, CH_2-O), 6.49 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.98–7.74 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.19 (1H, s, NH, D_2O -exchangeable) ppm; *m/z* (%) 448 (M^+ , 10), 275 (22), 183 (100), 173 (4), 155 (18), 145 (18), 115 (8) (Found : C, 66.37; H, 5.24; N, 5.96. $C_{25}H_{24}O_6N_2$ Calcd. : C, 66.96; H, 5.35; N, 6.25%).

6-Methyl-4-[3-(7-methyl-2-oxo-2H-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-pyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (4b) :

Colourless crystals, yield 91%, m.p. 290–292 °C; ν_{max} (KBr) : 1730 (lactone C=O), 1709 (ester C=O), 1648 (amide C=O), 1580 (C=C), 3351 (NH), 3234 (NH) cm^{-1} ; δ_H (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : 1.16 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz, CH_3 of $COOC_2H_5$), 2.33 (3H, s, CH_3 of Py-2-one), 2.46 (3H, s, C_6-CH_3), 4.07 (2H, q, *J* 6.9 Hz, CH_2 of $COOC_2H_5$), 5.22 (1H, s, CH of Py-2-one), 5.33 (2H, s, CH_2-O), 6.57 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.74–8.53 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.0 (1H, s, NH, D_2O -exchangeable) ppm (Found : C, 66.67; H, 5.04; N, 5.91. $C_{25}H_{24}O_6N_2$ Calcd. : C, 66.96; H, 5.35; N, 6.25%).

6-Methyl-2-oxo-4-[3-(3-oxo-3H-benzol[f]chromen-1-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-pyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (4c) :

Colourless crystals, yield 93%, m.p. 250–252 °C; ν_{max} (KBr) : 1727 (lactone C=O), 1710 (ester C=O), 1696 (amide C=O), 1578 (C=C), 3438 (NH), 3246 (NH) cm^{-1} ; δ_H (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : 1.12 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz, CH_3 of $COOC_2H_5$), 2.27 (3H, s, CH_3 of Py-2-one), 4.01 (2H, q, *J* 6.9 Hz, CH_2 of $COOC_2H_5$), 5.24 (1H, s, CH of Py-2-one), 5.67 (2H, s, CH_2-O), 6.81 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.97–8.25 (10H, m, Ar-H), 9.03 (1H, s, NH, D_2O -exchangeable) ppm (Found : C, 61.63; H, 4.61; N, 5.41. $C_{28}H_{24}O_6N_2$ Calcd. : C, 61.98; H, 4.95; N, 5.78%).

4-[3-(6-Methoxy-2-oxo-2H-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-6-methyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-pyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (4d) :

Colourless crystals, yield 87%, m.p. 188–190 °C; ν_{max} (KBr) : 1706 (lactone C=O), 1709 (ester C=O), 1647 (amide C=O), 1575 (C=C), 3441 (NH), 3245 (NH) cm^{-1} ; δ_H (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : 1.15 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH_3 of $COOC_2H_5$), 2.30 (3H, s, CH_3 of Py-2-one), 3.86 (3H, s, C_6-OCH_3), 3.99 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH_2 of $COOC_2H_5$), 5.26 (1H, s, CH of Py-2-one), 5.30 (2H, s, CH_2-O), 6.58 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.95–7.85 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.97 (1H, s, NH, D_2O -exchangeable) ppm (Found : C, 64.31; H, 4.81; N, 5.72. $C_{25}H_{24}O_7N_2$ Calcd. : C, 64.65; H, 5.17; N, 6.03%).

4-[3-(6-Chloro-2-oxo-2H-chromen-4-ylmethoxy)-phenyl]-6-methyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-pyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid ethyl ester (4e) :

Colourless crystals, yield 85%, m.p. 242–244 °C; ν_{max} (KBr) : 1715 (lactone C=O), 1700 (ester C=O), 1648 (amide C=O), 1560 (C=C), 3357 (NH), 3240 (NH) cm^{-1} ; δ_H (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : 1.15 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH_3 of $COOC_2H_5$), 2.29 (3H, s, CH_3 of Py-2-one), 4.04 (2H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH_2 of $COOC_2H_5$), 5.23 (1H, s, CH of Py-2-one), 5.33 (2H, s, CH_2-O), 6.63 (1H, s, C_3-H), 6.94–7.99 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.03 (1H, s, NH, D_2O -exchangeable) ppm (Found : C, 59.21; H, 4.01; N, 5.44. $C_{24}H_{21}O_6N_2Cl$ Calcd. : C, 59.50; H, 4.33; N, 5.78%).

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